

IN-FET
Ionic modulation for Epilepsy Treatment

Intermediate Update to the Dissemination Report

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1. Executive summary

This report provides a structured overview of the dissemination actions undertaken by the IN-FET project partners during the first two years of activity to ensure an appropriate degree of visibility of the project to all stakeholder categories, from the scientific community to the public. Despite COVID-19-related restrictions, numerous events and actions were undertaken and publications were prepared or submitted, as documented below. A brief outlook on the next year planned or expected actions is given in the last section and in the summary table. A copy of this public document is also available on www.zenodo.org.

2. Dissemination actions

For the first and second year of the IN-FET project, dissemination activities were primarily addressed to the public, rather than to a scientific audience. Given the COVID-19 lockdown and delays in early 2020, dissemination efforts have been focused mostly on the student's community (also as an aid toward the recruiting campaign in support of the project) and to the public (also by means of the website and the social media). Participation to hybrid or remote events allowed the project partners to spread the voice about the project. Engagement at the local or national level was also pursued, mainly via press releases, articles on the press or weekly magazines, etc.

2.1 Dissemination through websites and social media

The **IN-FET website** was launched in February 2020, as the first deliverable of the Management, RRI, Dissemination, Networking, Exploitation Work Package (WP5). Throughout the year, we regularly updated the sections "Events" and "Press and Dissemination" of the website, to announce the events involving the IN-FET project consortium, or to publish press release and divulgation articles that focused on the IN-FET project. Following the feedback from the expert, during our first review meeting, we redesigned the graphical outline of the website (<https://www.in-fet.eu>) and added an introductory video.

We also regularly broadcasted news, press-release, event alters by the IN-FET Twitter (79 followers) and Facebook (45 people liked the page) accounts to advertise our public talks or to engage with the public, discuss neuroprosthetics and give more visibility to our consortium.

We launched a **YouTube channel** (12 people subscribed to it, to date), where we uploaded the videos of our public outreach events: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC4299VceGDOSVqmFTgHTIEw> (200 total visualizations).

The description of the IN-FET project has also been published on our **consortium partner MCS' website**: <https://www.multichannelsystems.com/research-projects/fet>, on the website of the Neuronal Dynamics Laboratory at SISSA <https://www.giugliano.info/lab/doku.php> and on the Twitter, Facebook and LinkedIn profiles of several consortium members.

2.2 Dissemination through the press

After the kickoff meeting, in February 2020, a **press release**, written with the help of the press office in SISSA, was published on the website of SISSA, on the IN FET website and in the project's social accounts Twitter and Facebook. The press release briefly described the project, making its purpose accessible to all types of audience.

<https://www.in-fet.eu/doku.php/pressrelease1>
<http://phdneurobiology.sissa.it/eng/news/in-fet.aspx>
<https://www.sissa.it/news/eu-funds-%E2%82%AC3m-project-develop-nanodevices-against-epilepsy-and-parkinson%E2%80%99s>

A science **divulgarion article** was published in June 2020 in Panorama, an italian magazine. The title of the article was "Questioni di testa". In the article, Prof. Dr. Michele Giugliano explained how stimulating the brain with natural ionic currents (the basic principle behind the IN-FET project) may represent a new treatment for Parkinson.

https://www.in-fet.eu/lib/exe/detail.php/ebwdrvdxaipxci.jpeg?id=press_dissemination

An **article** about the IN-FET project was published in July 2020 in the monthly magazine of the University of Modena and Reggio Emilia. The title of the article was: "Oltre i confini: quattro progetti tra nanoelettronica, nanotecnologie e neuroscienze" and it described the aim of 4 Horizon 2020 funded projects, in the area of nanotechnologies and neurosciences. https://www.in-fet.eu/doku.php/webmagazine_unimodena

On February 23rd 2021, Prof. Dr. **Michele GIUGLIANO (SISSA)** has been guest of the radio show **RADAR** from the Italian Rai broadcasting, talking about the science dialogue between silicon neurons and biological neurons. The video of the talk has been uploaded on the IN-FET Youtube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tSJpPpzx2dI&t=267s>

On April 15 2021, for the International Day of Researchers, Prof. Dr. Michele Giugliano has been briefly interviewed by RAI, the Italian TV broadcasting company. The interview appeared in an article published by ANSA.it:

https://www.ansa.it/friuliveneziagiulia/notizie/2021/04/14/ansaricerca-fvg-studi-poli-eccellenza-ma-pochi-fondi_86bdd39-91d1-41eb-82f5-9ff8e56a6575.html

On 23 September 2021, the Italian newspaper "Corriere della Sera" published an article with the tile "Allo studio nanopacemaker contro epilessia e Parkinson" explaining the scope of the project IN-FET. <https://www.in-fet.eu/lib/exe/fetch.php/corriere-23-09-21.pdf>

2.3 Dissemination through scientific papers

2.3.1 Manuscripts under revision or preprints

1. *Spike–frequency adaptation is modulated by interacting currents in a Hodgkin-Huxley-type model: Role of the Na,K–ATPase*. **Renaud B. Jolivet**, Pierre J. Magistretti, 2020. Preprint: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.06.12.148437>; Altmetric score 7 (top 25%).
2. *On the role of theory and modeling in neuroscience*. Daniel Levenstein, Veronica A. Alvarez, Asohan Amarasingham, Habiba Azab, Richard C. Gerkin, Andrea Hasenstaub, Ramakrishnan Iyer, Renaud B. Jolivet, Sarah Marzen, Joseph D. Monaco, Astrid A. Prinz, Salma Quraishi, Fidel Santamaria, Sabyasachi Shivkumar, Matthew F. Singh, David B. Stockton, Roger Traub, Horacio G. Rotstein, Farzan Nadim, A. David Redish: Arxiv, 2020. Preprint: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2003.13825>; Altmetric score 66 (top 5%).
3. *Modelling of vertical nano-needles as sensing devices for neuronal signal recordings*. Federico Leva, Pierpaolo Palestri, Luca Selmi (2020). TechRxiv. Preprint. <https://doi.org/10.36227/techrxiv.12585086.v1>.
4. *Comparative performance of mutual information and transfer entropy for analyzing the balance of information flow and energy consumption at synapses*. Mireille Conrad and **Renaud B. Jolivet**, 2020. Preprint: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.06.01.127399>.
5. *Device simulations of ion-sensitive FETs with arbitrary surface chemical reactions*. L. J. Mele, P. Palestri and L. Selmi, 2021 Joint International EUROSIOI Workshop and International Conference on Ultimate Integration on Silicon (EUROSIOI-ULIS), 2021.
6. *Modeling non-equilibrium transport in ion-selective membrane/electrolyte interfaces with focus on FET-based potentiometric sensors*, Transactions on Electron Devices, L. J. Mele, P. Palestri, L. Selmi and M. A. Alam, 2021.
7. *State of the art and multiscale simulation analysis of micro/nano-electrodes for in-vitro neural sensing devices non-equilibrium transport in ion-selective membrane/electrolyte interfaces with focus on FET*, *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A*, F. Leva, P. Palestri and L. Selmi

2.3.2 Published

1. *Plasticity and Adaptation in Neuromorphic Biohybrid Systems*. Richard George, Michela Chiappalone, Michele Giugliano, Timothée Levi, Stefano Vassanelli, Johannes Partzsch, Christian Mayr. iScience. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2020.101589>
2. *General model and equivalent circuit for the chemical noise spectrum associated to surface charge fluctuation in potentiometric sensors*. L. J. Mele, P. Palestri and L. Selmi. IEEE Sensors Journal. <https://doi.org/10.1109/JSEN.2020.3038036>.

3. *Modelling Neuromodulated Information Flow and Energetic Consumption at Thalamic Relay Synapses*. Mireille Conrad and **Renaud B. Jolivet**. Lect. Notes Comput. Sci. 12397: 649-658 (2020). http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-61616-8_52.

2.4 Dissemination through other means

1. In February and March 2020, the IN-FET project coordinator, Prof. Dr. Michele Giugliano volunteered for two events (one lecture and one debate/interview) organised by SISSA for schools: a series of appointments where students from primary, middle and high school met the scientists working in SISSA and learned about the research they carry out, resulting often in enthusiastic reactions from both sides, the students and the professors.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Mjz4VCeKKsM>

2. In September 2020, in the frame of ESOF 2020 and Science in the City Festival, our IN-FET project coordinator Prof. Dr. Michele Giugliano, together with Prof. Dr. Pierpaolo Palestri and Prof. Dr. Luca Selmi, members of the IN-FET consortium, held a public lecture on ‘‘Nanotechnologies and nanoelectronics to cure the brain’’. Chairman of the talk was Dr. Valentina Perrera, IN-FET project manager. The public lecture took place inside the seminar room of the Revoltella Museum, downtown in Trieste and was streamed live on YouTube
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sHMQstkcw-o>

About 40 people were in the audience in Museo Revoltella in Trieste (Italy) and other 70 people followed the event live in the Science in the City Festival YouTube channel. The video available on the Science in the City Festival YouTube channel has now reached 445 views (updated to 19 September 2021). The video of the lecture is also permanently visible on the IN-FET YouTube channel, where it reached 77 views (updated to 19 September 2021).

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sHSjptNfqB8&t=702s>

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sHMQstkcw-o>

<https://events.scienceinthecity2020.eu/en/nanotechnologies-and-nanoelectronics-to-cure-the-brain>

3. We produced and distributed a leaflet to all consortium members and published on our website and social accounts, to synthetically describe the goal of the IN-FET project and the diversity of its consortium composition.
4. Prof. Dr. Michele Giugliano, together with Dr. Renaud Jolivet, participated as speakers to the MCAA Virtual Conference on Research and Democracy on the 6 November 2020 15:45 - 16:45 CET, with the talk: At the interface of AI, Neuroscience and Policy.
A summary of the workshop can be found here:
<https://medium.com/marie-curie-alumni/live-from-the-mcaa-virtual-conference-5e5a3114772c>
About 50 viewers listened to the live broadcast. Additionally, the recorded workshop is available on YouTube here <https://youtu.be/GMQQUvaIGJA> and here <https://youtu.be/kvPMzET9cOU>, and had accumulated approximately 162 views by September 2021. The workshop was heavily advertised on Twitter by multiple accounts before and after the event.
5. Prof. Dr. Michele Giugliano joined SISSA's ‘‘Student Day’’ on the 5th of March 2021, in a digital format, participating to a round table on Neuroscience and AI
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LjQCrdWmkLk> (49 views on September 19th 2021)
6. Prof. Dr. Pierpaolo Palestri (IUNet-Udine) taught a 14h course (March - June 2021) entitled ‘‘Interazione tra dispositivi elettronici e neuroni’’ (Interaction between electronic devices and

neurons) for the “Scuola Superiore” of the University of Udine. The course disseminates the results of the activities carried out by partner IUNET in the INFET project

7. We organized a joint FET meeting (online) with the HERMES-FET consortium (www.hermes-fet.eu) that took place on the 30 March 2021. Several speakers from HERMES-FET and INFET presented their results to pave the way for future collaboration.
8. Prof. Dr. Michele Giugliano presented a talk with the title, "Broad-band brains", for high-school students, within the SISSA for School programme on the 22 and 29 April 2021
9. Prof. Michele Giugliano gave an invited talk at the Como Lake summer school (Neural circuit complexity: Neuroscience, Models and Robotics (BrainCosmos), <https://brco.lakecomoschool.org> on the 1st of September 2021
10. Dr. Julian Mele, together with Prof. Dr. Pierpaolo Palestri joined the conference “EUROSOLULIS 2021” (Joint International EUROSOL Workshop and International Conference on Ultimate Integration on Silicon) held in Caen (France) on 1-4 Sep 2021 with an oral presentation entitled “*Device simulations of ion-sensitive FETs with arbitrary surface chemical reactions*”.
11. Prof. Renaud B. Jolivet participated to a high-level workshop to discuss the future of neurosciences and neurotechnologies “The Neuroscience Summit” on September 6-8, 2021 in Chetzeron, Switzerland.
12. Dr. Federico Leva (IUNET-UniMORE, PhD student partly funded by IN-FET) presented his research within the IN-FET project to the international advisory board of the PhD program in Information and Communication Technologies organized by Università di Modena and Reggio Emilia. The attendees were Professors of different disciplines from prestigious European Universities.
13. Dr. Diletta Pozzi, Dr. Valentina Perrera and Prof. Dr. Michele Giugliano presented the principle behind the IN-FET project, at the booth of SISSA at Trieste Next, a scientific research festival that takes place every year in Trieste, this year on the 24-26 September 2021. Within the same festival, on the 24 September, Prof. Dr. Michele Giugliano gave a lecture for high school students with the title: "Il futuro delle neuro-protesi"; and on the 26 September 2021 Dr. Diletta Pozzi and Dr. Michele Giugliano participated to a round table with the title: “AI & Microchips nel cervello: fantascienza o realta'?” <https://www.triestenext.it/tc-events/intelligenza-artificiale-e-microchip-nel-cervello-fantascienza-o-realta>
14. Gianmarco Gabrieli (IBM Research Europe, PhD student partly funded by IN-FET) presented to the 18th International Meeting on Chemical Sensors (IMCS, Chicago, May 31, 2021) the work on “*Quantification of Multi-Ion Mixtures Using A Machine Learning Assisted Integrated Electronic Tongue Leveraging Mobile and Cloud Platforms*”, including the advances on the development of polymeric films within the IN-FET project.

2.5 Planned dissemination events

- On 26-27 February 2022, Dr. Jannis Meents, Head of Research Projects at IN-FET consortium member MCS, will participate as speaker at the [2nd Workshop on Next Gen Organ-on-Chip & Organoids](https://www.csem.ch/page.aspx?pid=155967) (<https://www.csem.ch/page.aspx?pid=155967>), which is organized by the Centre Suisse d'Electronique et de Microtechnique (CSEM) in Switzerland. The talk will be entitled: “Next Generation Micro Electrode Array Devices”.

- Talks are on-going with partners of the BEFERROSYNAPTIC (www.beferrosynaptic.eu) H2020 project to organize a joint workshop later in 2021/early 2022 with invited and contributed talks.
- Prof. Renaud B. Jolivet will write a popular science column for the MCAA magazine Irradium to appear in 2022.

3. Summary table

Means of communication	Main target groups	Purpose	Actions done	Date	
IN-FET Twitter profile, IN-FET Facebook profile	ALL	To engage with the public, discuss about neuroprosthetics and give more visibility to the IN-FET project	Opening the profiles and posting periodically	February 2020	Twitter 79 followers; Facebook 45 likes, as of 19.09.2021
Project website	ALL	To create a web presence for the project and make the community aware of the IN-FET project's main aim and consortium composition	The website has been created and advertised on the social channels of IN-FET	February 2020	
YouTube channel	ALL	To upload the videos of our public outreach and scientific dissemination events	Opening the channel, uploading the videos, advertising the channel on the twitter and facebook accounts and on the IN-FET website	February 2020	12 subscribers as of 19.09.2021
Kickoff meeting press release	ALL	To communicate that the IN-FET project was launched and briefly describe its purpose	The press release was published on the website of SISSA, on the IN FET website and in the project's social accounts Twitter and Facebook	February 2020	
SISSA 4 Schools	high school students	To allow students from school to get in touch with scientists and familiarise with their research activities	A series of appointments where students from primary, middle and high school met the scientists working in SISSA and learned about the research they carry out	Periodically every year	
Science divulgation article by Panorama	ALL	To inform the public on the state-of-the-art technologies in neuroscience	Michele Giugliano explained how stimulating the brain with natural ionic currents (the basic principle behind the IN-FET project) may represent a new treatment for Parkinson	June 2020	
Article about the IN-FET project published in the monthly magazine of the University of Modena and Reggio Emilia	ALL, students, professors and staff, mainly from University of Modena and Reggio Emilia	To announce the involvement of UNIMORE in Horizon 2020 funded projects and describe these project's main aim	The article described the scientific focus of 4 different Horizon 2020 funded projects involving nanotechnologies, nano electronics and neuroscience	July 2020	
Public talk "Nanotechnologies and nanoelectronics to cure the brain"	ALL	To take part in the ESOF2020 conference with a public outreach event centered on IN-FET project	The public lecture took place inside the seminar room of the Revoltella Museum, downtown in Trieste and was streamed live on YouTube	September 2020	

Leaflet	ALL	To have a brochure for a quick presentation of IN-FET project's main aim and consortium composition	The leaflet highlights the most important aspects of the IN-FET project and summarises its goal. It has been distributed to all consortium members	November 2020	
Scientific publications or preprints in peer reviewed journals	Neuroscientists/scientists	Scientific dissemination of novel findings and results obtained within the IN-FET project	<p>Under revision or preprints</p> <p><i>Spike-frequency adaptation is modulated by interacting currents in an Hodgkin-Huxley-type model: Role of the Na,K-ATPase.</i> Renaud B. Jolivet, Pierre J. Magistretti, 2020. Preprint: https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.06.12.148437; Altmetric score 7 (top 25%).</p> <p><i>On the role of theory and modeling in neuroscience.</i> Daniel Levenstein, Veronica A. Alvarez, Asohan Amarasingham, Habiba Azab, Richard C. Gerkin, Andrea Hasenstaub, Ramakrishnan Iyer, Renaud B. Jolivet, Sarah Marzen, Joseph D. Monaco, Astrid A. Prinz, Salma Quraishi, Fidel Santamaria, Sabyasachi Shivkumar, Matthew F. Singh, David B. Stockton, Roger Traub, Horacio G. Rotstein, Farzan Nadim, A. David Redish: Arxiv, 2020. Preprint: http://arxiv.org/abs/2003.13825; Altmetric score 66 (top 5%).</p> <p><i>Modelling of vertical nano-needles as sensing devices for neuronal signal recordings.</i> Federico Leva, Pierpaolo Palestri, Luca Selmi (2020). TechRxiv. Preprint. https://doi.org/10.36227/techrxiv.12585086.v1.</p> <p><i>Comparative performance of mutual information and transfer entropy for analyzing the balance of information flow and energy consumption at synapses.</i> Mireille Conrad and Renaud B. Jolivet, 2020. Preprint: https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.06.01.127399.</p> <p><i>Device simulations of ion-sensitive FETs with arbitrary surface chemical reactions.</i> L. J. Mele, P. Palestri and L. Selmi, 2021 Joint International EUROSOI Workshop and International Conference on Ultimate Integration on Silicon (EUROSOI-ULIS), 2021.</p> <p><i>Modeling non-equilibrium transport in ion-selective membrane/electrolyte interfaces with focus on FET-based potentiometric sensors.</i> Transactions on Electron Devices, L. J. Mele, P. Palestri, L. Selmi and M. A. Alam, 2021.</p> <p><i>State of the art and multiscale simulation analysis of micro/nano-electrodes for in-vitro neural sensing devices non-equilibrium transport in ion-selective membrane/electrolyte interfaces with focus on FET.</i> Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A, F. Leva, P. Palestri and L. Selmi</p> <p>Published</p> <p><i>Plasticity and Adaptation in Neuromorphic Biohybrid Systems.</i> Richard George, Michela Chiappalone, Michele Giugliano, Timothée Levi, Stefano Vassanelli, Johannes Partzsch, Christian Mayr. iScience. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2020.101589</p> <p><i>General model and equivalent circuit for the chemical noise spectrum associated to surface charge fluctuation in potentiometric sensors.</i> L. J. Mele, P. Palestri and L. Selmi. IEEE Sensors Journal. https://doi.org/10.1109/JSEN.2020.3038036.</p>		

			<i>Modelling Neuromodulated Information Flow and Energetic Consumption at Thalamic Relay Synapses.</i> Mireille Conrad and Renaud B. Jolivet. Lect. Notes Comput. Sci. 12397: 649-658 (2020). http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-61616-8_52 .		
Online workshop	Neuroscientists/scientists	MCAA virtual conference on Research and democracy. A talk to discuss the interface between Neuroscience, AI and policy	A presentation by Prof. Dr. Michele Giugliano and Prof. Dr. Renaud Jolivet	November 2020	Reach as of Sept 2021, 162 viewers total
Public interview	ALL	To make divulgation on Italian top level scientific research in neurobiology	On Prof. Dr. Michele GIUGLIANO (SISSA) has been guest of the radio show RADAR from the Italian Rai broadcasting, talking about the science dialogue between silicon neurons and biological neurons. The video of the talk has been uploaded on the IN-FET Youtube channel: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tSjPpPzx2dL&t=267s	23 February 2021	
Online workshop	Neuroscientists/scientists	To pave the way for future collaborations a Joint lab meeting between the HERMES-FET and IN-FET project has been held online	Talks by scientists in both consortia	30 March 2021	
Course	University students	To inform students about research activities on the edge between electronics and neuroscience	14h course held by Prof. Dr. Pierpaolo Palestri (in Italian) entitled "Interazione tra dispositivi elettronici e neuroni" (Interaction between electronic devices and neurons) for the "Scuola Superiore" of the University of Udine	March-June 2021	7 students
Public interview	ALL	To make divulgation on Italian top level scientific research in neurobiology	In occasion of the International Day of Researchers, Prof. Dr. Michele Giugliano has been briefly interviewed by the RAI, the Italian TV broadcasting company. The interview resulted in an article published in ANSA.it: https://www.ansa.it/friuliveneziagiulia/notizie/2021/04/14/ansaricerca-fvg-studi-poli-eccellenza-ma-pochi-fondi_86bdd39-91d1-41eb-82f5-9ff8e56a6575.html	15 April 2021	
Conference presentation	scientists	To present results on development of polymeric films on miniaturized electrodes	Gianmarco Gabrieli presented "Quantification of Multi-Ion Mixtures Using A Machine Learning Assisted Integrated Electronic Tongue Leveraging Mobile and Cloud Platforms" at 18 th IMCS conference 2021 held in Chicago, USA	May 31 2021	
Conference presentation	scientists	To present results obtained in the Neuronal Dynamics Laboratory in SISSA	Prof. Michele Giugliano has been invited to give a talk with the title "Correlation Transfer in Cortical Neurons" at the Como Lake summer school (Neural circuit complexity: Neuroscience, Models and Robotics (BrainCosmos)), https://brco.lakecomoschool.org	September 1, 2021	
Conference presentation	scientists	To present modelling results to the scientific community	Dr. Julian Mele, together with prof. Pierpaolo Palestri Talk entitled "Device simulations of ion-sensitive FETs with arbitrary surface chemical reactions" at the conference "EUROSOI-ULIS 2021" held in Caen France	September 1-4, 2021	Approx. 70 participants
Online workshop	Scientists	To discuss the future of neurosciences and neurotechnologies	Renaud B. Jolivet participated with a talk to "The Neuroscience Summit" in Chetzeron, Switzerland	September 6-8, 2021	
Science divulgation article by Corriere della Sera	ALL	To explain to a broad public the scope of the IN-FET project	The Italian newspaper Corriere della Sera published an article with the tile "Allo studio nanopacemaker contro epilessia e Parkinson" explaining the scope of the project IN-FET. https://medialab.sissa.it/rassegna-tsnex/system/files/images/rassegna-tsnex/corriere-23-09-21.pdf	23 September 2021	

Trieste NEXT	ALL	To take part in the Trieste next scientific festival with a public outreach event centered on IN-FET project	Lecture for high school students with the title: "Il futuro delle neuro-protesi; round table with the title: "AI & Microchips nel cervello: fantascienza o realta'?""; presence of the IN-FET project representatives at the SISSA booth.	24-26 September 2021	
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Table1. Summary of the dissemination activities per target community and action.

4. Conclusions and outlook

The first two years of the project led to a more than adequate total number of dissemination actions, especially toward the public, understandably so in view of the delays and difficulties related to the COVID-19 pandemic. Links to other projects in the same or similar research areas have been established which are expected to enhance the effectiveness of the outcomes and expand the perimeter of stakeholders reached. As project activities are beginning to produce results of scientific relevance, IN-FET partners will steer their main dissemination actions toward scientific papers on peer reviewed journals and conferences.